

**THE ROLE OF PSYCHOLOGICAL SERVICE IN PROFESSIONAL
FORMATION OF ADOLESCENT STUDENTS.**

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Abstract: Currently, professional psychology has its own special subject, its own special tasks and its own special examination methods. There are several psychological organizations, educational institutions, and publishing houses related to the field of professional psychology. Scientific associations of professional psychologists, societies of psychologists are working. Conferences and congresses on psychological problems are being held in our republic and internationally. The science of psychology, its scientific and practical importance is now recognized by everyone. This article provides information about the role of psychological services in the professional development of adolescent students.

Key words: Psychological problems, adolescence, motivation, psychological factor, profession.

The next stage after adolescence can be considered as one stage, but it can also be divided into two stages according to the current classification of most psychologists. During this period, the student will be physically strong, able to work independently after graduation, and will have the opportunity to try himself in a higher school. Another characteristic of this period is that work and education are equally important. Active participation in social life, changes in the character of education, scientific worldview in boys and girls, leads to the formation of stable faith, the emergence of a high human feeling, creative approach to the acquisition of knowledge. makes great demands on his psyche. The role of psychological factors is increasing in all areas. Attention is being paid to a person's memory, thinking, perception, temperament characteristics, reaction speed. Because the fact that a person does not make serious mistakes at work and does not spoil the work depends on his mental and personal qualities in many ways. For this reason, the importance of the science of psychology in the correct organization of the "Man - machine" system is increasing. This leads to the strengthening of connections between technical sciences and psychology, to their introduction into each other.

The leading factor in early adolescence is a radical change in the nature, essence and content of the activity of a high school student. First of all, the shift in self-awareness is clearly visible in adolescents. This score doesn't just mean growth. In a teenager, the desire to determine his spiritual world, personal qualities, intelligence, abilities and opportunities increases. Students of this age have characteristics related to self-awareness. First, they will have the opportunity to

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more accurately assess their strengths and weaknesses, achievements and shortcomings, appropriate and inappropriate behavior. Although a teenager can fully imagine the features of his spirituality and psyche compared to a teenager, he allows shortcomings in their rational assessment. As a result, he overestimates his own characteristics, becomes arrogant, arrogant, and begins to behave abnormally towards the members of the class and pedagogic teams. Also, some teenagers underestimate their own behavior, mental abilities and interests and try to behave modestly. Another characteristic of a child in adolescence is a tendency to respect, feel and be proud of one's own dignity, duty, conscience, which is reflected in complex interpersonal relationships. For example, a young man and a young girl understand sensitivity as understanding the difference between delicate and elegant situations, realizing the need, organizing help objectively, and doing it without affecting the individual's personality. A teenager evaluates his good intentions from the point of view of determining his place in the team, for example, "Am I suitable for my chosen specialty?" "Can I contribute to the development of society?" looks for answers to the questions. In order to create a clear idea of his own virtue in the student, the teacher should help him very skillfully and intelligently. Only then will the team feel deep respect and gratitude for their teacher and friends.

In the psychology of professional activity, self-observation (introspection) is also used. Often, an experienced psychologist or a highly skilled professional can draw a scientific conclusion through self-observation. For example, by monitoring his thinking, he gets information about emotional changes in himself, as well as about the emergence and passing of internal mechanisms of thinking. As a result, he observes the quality, content, essence of thinking and how, at what speed, in what form: it happens. One of the important aspects of the triangle of guidance for choosing a profession is the presence of certain knowledge about the requirements for the owner of this profession. The second characteristic of it is that knowledge is embodied in the employment opportunities of the society (province, city, district) in relation to this or that specialty. Another unique aspect is that the knowledge about the diligence, ability, and personal characteristics of the one who is directed to the profession is summarized, and all aspects related to the choice of profession are summarized.

Teenagers make more mistakes because they don't have a clear idea about choosing a profession. They do not understand what personal qualities the chosen or required profession requires. Because they are not able to rationally assess their abilities, they do not know how quickly and accurately they can act when acquiring this or that profession, the features of perception and perception, and the coordination of the nervous system. That is why they make the mistakes described

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above. However, in the present era, there are ways to prevent such unfortunate situations. For this, it is appropriate to pay special attention to the following general aspects of pedagogical, psychological and social characteristics. World psychologists who have studied the problem of study motivations find it necessary to divide them into two categories or groups. Motives belonging to the first category are directly combined with the content and essence of educational activities, as well as its processes and conditions. The system of motives belonging to the second category depends on the wide-scale interaction of students with the environment, their desire to interact with strangers, and their personal view of social reality.

One of the ways to guide the choice of a profession and to promote it is to display visual aids, photo booths, book exhibitions, to display the products of the creative work of young artists and naturalists, and to exhibit the works of painters and technicians. In addition, it is possible to arouse interest in this or that profession by organizing excursions to museums. Praxic qualities (enjoyment, enjoyment) formed in adolescents increase their love for the profession and strengthen it. Representatives of labor psychology recommend different methods of choosing a profession. In particular, deepening the polytechnic nature and characteristics of teaching all subjects; use of surrounding production as an object in sciences in the natural-mathematical field; organizing activities using local history materials in the teaching of social sciences, raising students' interest in the profession and morally preparing them for work; providing information about the profession while acquiring the basics of science; is to create conditions for independent familiarization of the profession chooser about the fields of work. It is impossible to solve the problems of professional psychodiagnostics (professional psychological) without analyzing professional activity, that is, it is necessary to pay attention to the essence of professionography and its structure. Only then can an active approach be implemented, and its actions and operations can be evaluated with the help of tests. Because movements and operations make up the content of this activity, their comparative description facilitates the acquisition process, creates a basis for choosing people capable of it. Sorting, justifying tests for diagnosing and evaluating the effectiveness of the activity, allows to determine the criterion of its success. As a result of summarizing the results of professionography, (professionogram), it becomes possible to classify (classify) professions. Professional activity consists of attitudes and motives of a person, includes control and management of movements and operations. To study the dynamic features of the activity, it is necessary to implement a multi-faceted approach to it. It is not possible to describe the essence of professional activity by

taking into account only motivational and regulatory aspects, if this is the case, it is necessary to include its personal, emotional, cognitive and operational, voluntary aspects in the subject of research. The analysis of professional activity allows to determine the criteria that serve to evaluate its success. This is absolutely necessary to check the stability and validity of the tests. . A student with negative motivation will continue to participate in the educational process by choosing a path that is less difficult (difficult situation). Students related to such study motivation will not have the opportunity to achieve high scores and successful learning, because the feeling of participating in the lesson without passion, the lack of knowledge and interest in the subject of study is a moral obstacle to this. serves as As a result of this, the number of non-assimilating, slow assimilating, slow students is expanding, and if this thing becomes a daily habit, it can grow to the level of a stereotype. Independent and successful study requires active, persistent, creative research from a person and puts similar demands on the learner. Due to the fact that the person is not ready for these situations, due to the limitations of his opportunities, he will fill the ranks of those who do not master, study in the same class or course for two years, and with all these difficulties, he will complete his class and course. It is possible to achieve positive results by reconsidering the motivation of students of this category.

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